

THE PLACE OF HARMFUL MAMMALS IN HUMAN LIFE AND SIGNIFICANCE IN NATURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10320700>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 01-December 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 04- December 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 09- December 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Biological diversity, animal husbandry, fur farming, poultry farming, Bukhara, Uzbekistan, Ukraine, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Europe, Siberia, CIS.

ABSTRACT

The article contains information about the role of mammals in human activities and in nature, which have some harmful properties found in nature. In nature, it is important to maintain biodiversity by managing the number of animal species.

Today, special attention is being paid to the protection and rational use of the animal world, which is an important component of biological diversity on a global scale. In particular, the wide and sometimes irregular use of the animal world for hunting, existing problems in the field of management of hunting farms, in most cases cause the extinction of species or a decrease in their number. As a result, some species are becoming rare or endangered species. Accordingly, the in-depth study of these issues, the development of appropriate recommendations for their solution, and the regulation of hunting farms are of urgent importance today. In addition, due to the sustainable use of hunted species, it is possible to increase the economic and social well-being of the population.

In particular, animals have acquired a relatively perfect structure during the long historical development, as well as being able to adapt to very different living conditions.

Mammals can be found in places ranging from polar regions to tropical forests, including taiga, steppe - mountains, fields, meadows, deserts, mountains, and inhabited areas. Aquatic mammals also live in rivers, lakes, seas and oceans. We know that flying creatures, like birds, occupy air spaces.

These animals play an extremely important role in human life. Most of them are useful in one way or another and are worth preserving and protecting. As a result of inappropriate use of the animal world, more than a hundred species of animals have been completely exterminated in the past history of mankind, and this is especially important now. Among the extinct mammals, there are valuable animals such as the ox tarpan horse, which is the ancestor of the domestic cow, and the sea cow, which can provide meat for half of humanity. In the CIS, a lot of work has been done to restore the number of hooves of valuable animals such as saigas, which at the beginning of the 20th century were only a few tens of heads, but

now their number has increased to two million. The number of moose in the European part of the CIS, and the number of sable in Siberia have been restored. The number of sea beavers, which are almost extinct, is increasing in the Far East.

Wild animals are hunted to obtain various products (fur, meat, oil, skin, musk, etc.). In addition, these animals are hunted for sport and hobby. Approximately one third of the mammals living in Uzbekistan can be considered as potential objects. In the republic, muskrat is the most important for hunting, followed by foxes and skunks, which are rarely hunted in recent years.

Despite the end of industrial hunting and the decrease in the demand for its fur, poaching of this species was recorded throughout the republic, including in the Bukhara region. In December 2018, illegal hunting of 98 muskrats was found in Lake Karagyr. Illegal hunting of this species is observed every year in collectors in the region. According to the data, in 2019, it was found that 1,505 muskrat furs were illegally transported to neighboring Kazakhstan.

In nature, it is quite difficult to classify different types of animals as harmful animals. Because one species can have different importance in different natural and ecological conditions. We have especially rodents - synanthropes: rats, house mice, they can be harmful by entering residential areas, including rats destroying products in houses and warehouses, as well as destroying eggs and chicks and piglets in chicken farms. In addition, rats and rodents also spread ectoparasites (fleas, lice, ticks, etc.) that spread dangerous diseases (plague). House mice also eat food and are considered a source of cholera and tularemia. In the southern districts, mice and rats move to crops in the summer and cause great damage. It is known in science that common field mouse (M. socialis), which is widespread in many districts, especially in the years of spring rainfall, causes a lot of damage to agriculture. In addition, forest mice (Apodemus sylvaticus, A. flavicollis) also cause damage. From the period of ripening of grains and grains, before their ripening, weevils cause significant damage to grain. Among them, 2 figures (Citellus pygmaeus) should be mentioned separately, which is spread in the deserts and oases of Uzbekistan in the south of Ukraine, near the Caucasus and in the north-west of Kazakhstan.

There are no harmful predators in the fauna of the world. You should not lose even a wolf that has a lot of damage. In districts where there are no livestock and fur farms, the wolf benefits by eating sick animals and sanitizing them in nature. The attitude towards foxes and other wild animals should be handled more carefully and gently. First of all, the fox was a precious fur animal that took the first place in fur production.

In the following years, due to the gathering of foxes and wild boars near hunting farms and residential areas, their number is increasing year by year and it leads to the manifestation of some negative situations.

However, it cannot be around poultry farms. In addition, it is necessary to consider the benefits of foxes and other predators in the elimination of pests. For example, examination of stomachs and faeces of several foxes showed that 60-100% of their diet was rodents, and in some cases 8-35% was birds. White mice and skunks are mainly murine rodents.

Tiger, leopard and wildebeest are rare and should be protected. Brown bear, wolverine, and others should be treated with care. Polar bear hunting is prohibited. There are also a number

of mammals that transmit infectious diseases to humans. Diseases that infect both animals and humans are called anthroozoonoses. These include cholera, tularemia, leishmaniasis, rickettsiosis, spirochetosis, encephalitis, and other diseases.

1 picture. leishmaniasis (*Leishmania*)

Woodpeckers, sand mice, and rats spread a dangerous disease called cholera. This disease bacteria (*Pasterella pastis*) is transmitted to humans when they come into direct contact with animals, for example, when they bite or through their fleas. Tularemia sometimes turns into an epidemic, and a lot of people get sick. The causative agent of the disease (*Francisella tularensis*) is transmitted to a person through indirect skin contact with blood-sucking insects (flies, mosquitoes, fleas, lice). Indirect rodents carrying germs can primarily be water rats, water voles (*Arvicola amphibius*), common field mice, house mice, voles, rabbits. One of the simple animals that spread leishmaniasis (*Leishmania*) is transmitted to humans through mosquitoes. A very serious and dangerous disease affecting the nervous system - encephalitis - is transmitted by invisible filtering viruses. Many animals (rodents, insects) are virus carriers. The virus is transmitted to humans through ticks and mosquitoes. Investigations by E.N. Pavlovsky show that the spread of zoonotic diseases in nature has a focal (local) character. Natural hotbeds are places with optimal conditions for the growth of disease-causing organisms.

Based on the study of natural foci, the Pavlovsky school developed measures to prevent diseases and eliminate foci. This work also requires extensive work in the field of vertebrate biology, the main microbe spreader.

The fight against agricultural pests and rodents that spread epidemic diseases is being carried out on a large scale. In carrying out these works, annual changes in the number of rodents, their occurrence in natural conditions and in places where people live are considered. Eliminating rodents is particularly effective in years when their numbers are low. In such years, since rodents are scattered sporadically and often in small territories, it is easy to fight

against them. In the fight against rodents, 3 main methods are used: biological, mechanical and chemical.

Biological control is based on the protection and attraction of birds of prey and mammals that feed on rodents. It is forbidden to hunt foxes, white mice, skunks, etc. from fur animals in districts with a high risk of disease occurrence. This way significantly reduces the number of rodents. In places where people live, rodents are infected with acute diseases that do not harm humans and farm animals, for example, Isachenko's bacterium. Adding toxic chemicals (chrysid or naphthylurea) to their food is also effective.

The mechanical method consists of catching rodents with various traps. The chemical control method is based on poisoning rodents with gaseous poison in their nest or adding poison to their food. In the first case, chlorpicrin and cyanplav are used. In case of poisoning with chlorpicrine, earth or tampon saturated with this poison is placed in the nest. Many useful animals and birds die when using feed with strong poisons such as zinc phosphide and barium fluoroacetate. This method, which is harmful in some cases, should not be used.

By the 1990s, the complete end of industrial hunting and the degradation of natural habitats caused the re-gathering of wild boars and foxes to feed around urban landscapes in the conditions of the Bukhara region, and sometimes harming poultry farming. Secondly, the meeting of foxes and wild boars near residential areas, their trophic contact with dogs and cats and other animals can lead to the spread and transmission of various dangerous diseases (scabies, rabies). For example, in 2002, state inspectors, foresters and local residents of Ugom-Chotkal National Park and Chotkal Nature Reserve killed wolves, wild boars and foxes due to scabies disease in this park and reserve. In 2010, it was noted that there were foxes and chiabors infected with scabies in Parkent forestry. On this basis, it is necessary to establish preventive measures aimed at eliminating this problem, i.e. management of the number of foxes, wild boars, wild dogs and cats.

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